

STUDIES ON LIGNITES OF SOUTH INDIA. PART III. XYLENE AND BENZENE EXTRACTS FROM SOUTH ARCOT LIGNITES

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Doubts have been expressed about the montan wax content in South Arcot lignite. Samples from different depths were extracted with pure xylene and benzene. It is found that the percentage of crude wax is below 10 and that it does not change by storage over a long period. The wax content may be higher at depths greater than 300 feet.

Srikantan and Shenoy¹ had reported values up to 69.7% of wax content obtained by extracting lignites from South Arcot with xylene. Doubts have been expressed whether such a large amount of wax would be found in the bulk samples of lignite. John² reported 4.82% and 3.18% extract with benzene from two samples on the pure coal (moisture and ash-free) basis. Whitaker³ stated, "extracts of waxy material and crude wax amounting to 5 to 10% of the dry lignite have been obtained".

So in order to find out whether a high yield of wax is obtainable from South Arcot lignite and whether there is any relation between wax content and depth of the lignite bed, samples previously received from the Neyveli lignite mines have been extracted on a laboratory scale.

EXPERIMENTAL

The samples were crushed to 60 mesh, air-dried for 2 hours, packed in filter paper sheets and extracted in a Soxhlet, using xylene and benzene for 6 hours or more till the soxhleting solvent was colorless. The solvent was then distilled off and the extract weighed. This (crude extract) was then extracted with ether. The ether-insoluble portion is the pure montan wax. The values obtained are shown in Table I as per cent on the moisture-free basis,

TABLE I

No.	Sample.	Xylene extract.		Benzene extract.	
		Crude.	Purified or ether-insoluble wax.	Crude.	Purified or ether-insoluble wax.
1	90' seam	5.00%	1.77%	...	...
2	154'-156'	3.92	1.92	4.28%	2.04%
3	170'-175'	3.67	1.17	3.57	1.34
4	199'-205'	4.27	1.52	3.23	1.17
5	234'6"-242'6"	3.41	1.25	...	...
6	258'-264'	3.83	1.35	...	...
7	303'-305'	6.69	2.17	...	...
8	350'-379'	6.77	2.61	...	...
9	416'-417'6"	8.71	3.33	5.80	2.20

Benzene generally gives a lower yield than xylene at its boiling point and atmospheric pressure. This is in agreement with the results obtained by Cawley and King in their work on the effect of different solvents on wax yield⁴.

As the samples were collected sometime back and as lignite disintegrated into powdery form on keeping, it was thought desirable to determine whether there was any decrease in the wax content with storage. Three samples, the wax content of which was determined formerly, were again extracted under the same conditions as before. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Date.	Previous results.		Present results-March '54.	
		Crude wax.	Pure wax.	Crude wax.	Pure wax.
1	Sep. 1952	5.2	2.0	5.1	2.1
2	Nov. 1952	3.5	1.2	3.6	1.4
3	Jan. 1953	4.3	1.7	4.4	1.6

The wax content of South Arcot lignite is generally below 10%. From Table II it may be concluded that the wax content does not change with storage. The wax content seems to be higher at depths greater than 300 ft.

REFERENCES

1. Srikantan & Shenoy, this *Journal*, 1951, 14, 2.
2. John, Lurgi Co., Private communication on trials made on utilisation of South Arcot lignite.
3. Whitaker, Private communication: "Brief Report of work done on South Arcot lignite (Brown coal)."
4. Cawley & King, "The Extraction of Ester waxes from British lignite and peat." Fuel Research Technical Paper No. 52 (Britain), 1946, p. 16.